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**ORGANIC CARBON IN SEMIARID SOIL PROFILES: VERTICAL
DISTRIBUTION, CONTROL FACTORS AND IMPACT OF LAND USE AND
CLIMATE CHANGE**

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ABSTRACT

Purpose. The sensitivity of soil organic carbon (SOC) to global change drivers, according to the depth profile is receiving increasing attention because of its importance in the global C cycle and its potential feedback to climate change. A better knowledge of the vertical distribution of SOC and its controlling factors – the aim of this study - will help scientists predict the consequences of global change.

Material and Methods. The study area was the Murcia Province (S.E. Spain) under semiarid Mediterranean conditions. The database used consists of 312 soil profiles collected in a systematic grid, each 12 km² covering a total area of 11004 km². Statistical analysis to study the relationships between SOC concentration and control factors in different soil use scenarios was conducted at fixed depths of 0-20 cm, 20-40 cm, 40-60 cm and 60-100 cm.

Results and Discussion. Significant differences in SOC concentration were found in the top 40 cm according to land use, soil type and lithology, while below this depth no differences were observed. The ANOVA showed that land use was the most important

1 factor controlling SOC concentration in 0-40 cm depth. Significant differences were
2 found in the relative importance of environmental and textural factors according to land
3 use and soil depth. In forestland precipitation and texture were the main predictor
4 variables, while in cropland and shrubland the main predictors were temperature and
5 lithology. Total SOC stored in the top 1m in the region was about 79 Tg (Teragram)
6 with low mean density ($\approx 7 \text{ kg C m}^{-3}$). The vertical distribution showed differences
7 between uses being shallower in forestland and deeper in cropland. Losses of about
8 25% in SOC stock in the 0-100 cm soil layer could be expected as a result of converting
9 forestland into cropland, these losses being highest in the upper horizons. A reduction in
10 rainfall would have a negative impact on SOC in forestland and shrubland, and an
11 increase of temperature would adversely affect SOC in croplands and shrubland. With
12 increasing depth, the relative importance of climatic factors decreases and texture
13 becomes more important in controlling SOC in all land uses.

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31 *Conclusions.* The negative impacts referred above would be much greater in surface
32 SOC. So, strategies for C sequestration should be focused on subsoil sequestration,
33 which was hindered in forestland due to bedrock limitations to soil depth. In these
34 conditions, sequestration in cropland through appropriate management practices is
35 recommended.

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46 **Key words:** Soil organic matter, climatic change, carbon sequestration potential, land
47 use and global change.

48 49 50 51 52 53 **1. Introduction**

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Soil carbon is an important component of the global carbon cycle since it represents twice the amount of carbon found in the atmosphere and about 75 % of the total terrestrial organic carbon pool (Prentice, 2001). The sensitivity of decomposition of soil organic carbon (SOC) to global change drivers is receiving increasing attention, because of its importance in the global C cycle and potential feedback to climate change (Davidson and Janssens, 2006; von Lützow and Kögel-Knabner, 2009). However, there is little agreement concerning the effects of global warming on SOC stocks - a major source of uncertainty in future climate change predictions (Powlson, 2005; Schmidt et al. 2011).

The storage of organic carbon (OC) in the soil depends on the balance between gains and losses of C. Biotic controls, like biomass productivity and microbial abundance, environmental controls, like precipitation and temperature, soil characteristics like, texture and lithology and anthropogenic controls, like land use and management, influence the processes of SOC storage or losses. A clear description of the distribution and changes of SOC and its controlling factors will help predict the consequences of climate change.

Most of the studies related with the factors controlling SOC concentration have been restricted to the surface soil horizon and only a few include the total soil profile. However, more than 50 % of the total SOC is stored in the subsoil (Batjes, 1996). Jobbagy and Jackson (2000) reported that in temperate grasslands 59 % of SOC is located between 20 and 100 cm depth. Consequently, minor shifts in these subsoil stocks of organic C will have considerable impact on the entire C balance (Don et al. 2007).

Carbon turnover models tend to assume that the mechanisms controlling C dynamics are the same in both topsoil and subsoil (Jenkinson and Coleman, 2008). However,

1 there is sufficient evidence to suggest that the factors controlling C dynamics in topsoil
2 and subsoil may be different and, yet, this possibility has not really been considered or
3 investigated (Salomé et al. 2010). In this regard, some research has shown that
4 subsurface SOC is significantly more sensitive to increases in temperature or nutrient
5 availability than surface SOC (Fierer et al. 2003), while for others upper SOC is more
6 sensitive to climate and texture than deeper SOC (Liu et al. 2011; Jobbagy and Jackson,
7 2000).

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17 On the other hand, soil C sequestration has been consistently defined as an important
18 component of a comprehensive greenhouse management strategy for climatic change
19 mitigation (Pacala and Socolow, 2004). However, the potential of soil to sequester C
20 and thus to mitigate climate change remains controversial (Smith, 2005). Several studies
21 have proven that it is feasible to restore the organic carbon lost in degraded soils. For
22 example, twenty years after of a single addition of organic compost, Albaladejo et al.
23 (2008) reported an increase in SOC stock of 9.5 Mg ha⁻¹ in the upper 20 cm of a
24 semiarid degraded soil included in the area covered by this study. To increase our
25 knowledge of the soil's potential for climate change mitigation it is the utmost
26 importance to investigate the impact of the key factors controlling the levels of organic
27 matter in soils, in order to identify optimal strategies for land management (Chaplot et
28 al. 2010).

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46 Despite several studies on global SOC inventories, quantitative data on the relationship
47 between SOC concentration and the controlling factors do not exist at a large scale (Lal,
48 2004), a lack that is especially significant in semiarid areas (Hoffmann et al. 2012). The
49 paucity of data on soil carbon distribution in the profile in different landscapes has been
50 identified as one of the major knowledge gaps in soil science (Lal et al. 1998).
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1 The aims of this study were: i) to establish the vertical distribution of SOC in three
2 different land uses with contrasting lithology and soil type throughout the Murcia
3 Province, ii) to determine the main factors controlling variation in SOC concentration at
4 different depths and for different land uses, and iii) to increase our ability to predict the
5 impact of global change drivers on SOC concentration in semiarid areas.
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10 We hypothesized that in semiarid areas the factors controlling SOC levels change with
11 soil depth and that those factors may depend on the land use.
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19 **2. Material and Methods**

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24 *2.1. Study area*

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28 The study area was located in Murcia Province, southeast Spain (38° 45' - 37° 23' North
29 and 0° 41' - 2° 21' West). The climate is semiarid Mediterranean, where maximum
30 temperatures coincide with minimum rainfall levels. The mean annual temperature is 17
31 °C, the potential evapotranspiration about 900 mm, and mean annual rainfall 330 mm.
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33 The lithological substrate is composed mainly of limestone materials. Climax vegetation
34 of the area has been mainly attributed either to the mesomediterranean or
35 thermomediterranean thermotypes of the Murcia-Almeriense Province.
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45 *2.2. Data source*

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49 The present study was based on the data from LUCDEME (Combating Desertification
50 in the Mediterranean Area) project. This project started in Spain in 1981 on the
51 initiative of UN Conference on Desertification of Nairobi in 1977, and is in force at
52 present. The soil database of Murcia Province was collected between 1986 and 1998
53 and characterizes 312 soil profiles with a total of 913 samples and site descriptions. The
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1 profiles were collected in a systematic grid every 12 km², representing a total surface
2 area of 11004 km². The analytical data were recorded at fixed depth intervals of 0-20
3 cm, 20-40 cm, 40-60 cm and 60-100 cm. This database seeks to characterize the
4 diversity of soils and land uses and environments in the study area.
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9 Each profile provided information on soil organic carbon concentration (g kg⁻¹), land-
10 use, soil type, altitude, lithology, soil texture and volumetric stone fraction. For this
11 study, the land uses were grouped into three classes: forestland, shrubland and cropland.
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13 An area was considered forestland when trees were present and no distinctions were
14 made as regards the density. Shrubland use includes typical Mediterranean matorral
15 (*Rosmarinus*, *Thymus*, *Stipa*) and abandoned croplands recovered by matorral, with a
16 vegetal cover ranging between (50-70%). Most of the cropland is dedicated to irrigated
17 crops (cereals, fruit trees and citrus) and a small proportion is not irrigated (cereals and
18 almonds). Of all the soil profiles analysed, 46.7% represented croplands, 39%
19 forestlands and 14.3% shrublands.
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24 The samples were representative of the most characteristics soil and lithology types in
25 the region. The soil types were: 39.1% of the profiles were Calcisols, 20.2% Regosol,
26 14.5% Fluvisols and 26.2% Cambisols, Leptosols, Kastanozems and Solonchaks. The
27 distribution by lithology was: 60% of the profiles were developed from Quaternary
28 sediments, 15% from Alluvial sediments, 16% from Marls and 9% from Metamorphic
29 sediments. As regards the relation between soil type and land use, Calcisols, Cambisols
30 and Regosols were not associated with any particular use and can be found under all the
31 land uses; Kastannozems and Leptosols only appeared in forestland and shrubland;
32 Fluvisols was predominantly associated with cropland and Solonchacks with shrubland.
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34 Mean annual precipitation and mean annual temperature (T) at the sampling sites were
35 estimated from available monthly climate datasets (73 stations) for the period 1966-
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2006. Based on the high negative correlation between altitude and temperature ($r=-0.89$) values of T were corrected for each sampling point through Kriging with External Drift using altitude as drift variable.

The altitude of the sampling points ranged between 0 and 1700 m, with an average value for forestlands that was double that of shrublands and croplands. The mean temperature of the sampling points ranged between 11 °C and 18 °C being higher in shrublands and croplands (16.4) than in forestlands (15.3) reflecting the higher altitude in the last. The average precipitation of the sampling points varied between 200 mm and 550 mm, the highest mean values being for forestlands. Temperatures higher than 17 °C were observed, mostly in areas located at altitudes lower than 700 m and temperatures lower than 14°C applied mainly to in areas located at altitudes greater than 700 m altitude.

2.3. Soil organic carbon density and stocks estimation

The soil organic carbon density (SOC_{CD} kg m⁻²) in each layer interval was determined by the product of SOC concentration, thickness of the layer interval and the bulk density in each soil layer. SOC_{CD} was also corrected for the volumetric gravel content of each soil layer.

$$\text{SOC}_{CD} (\text{Kg m}^{-2}) = \sum_i^n \text{BD}_i * \text{SOC}_{\text{conc}, i} * \text{layer thickness}_i * (1 - F_i/100) \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

where n is the number of sampled depth intervals, BD_i , $\text{SOC}_{\text{conc}, i}$ and F_i represent bulk density, SOC concentration and % of gravel (>2mm) in each interval i, respectively.

Given that the LUCDEME data base does not include soil bulk density data, this parameter was estimated from a pedotransfer function (PTF). To select the PTF that

1 best fits in the study area, different PTFs were tested, using 118 analytical data from the
2 other soil studies in the region. Two of the tested PTFs were internationally referenced
3 (Tomasella and Hodnett, 1998 and Bernoux et al. 1998), and the other, Barahona and
4 Santos Frances (1981) was developed from data of soil profiles representative of
5 Southeastern Spain, where our study area is located. The tests showed the following
6 Pearson correlation coefficient: Barahona and Santos Frances (r=0.673, p=0.000);
7 Tomasella and Hodnett, 1998 (r=0.309, p=0.001); and Bernoux et al. 1998 (r=0.007,
8 ns). From these results the following equation of Barahona and Santos Frances was
9 selected:
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$$23 \quad \text{B.D (g cm}^{-3}\text{)} = 1.5456 + (\% \text{ sand} * 0.0015) - (\% \text{ clay} * 0.0022) - (\% \text{ OC} * 0.1219) \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

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26 The authors point to an R² of 0.45 for this equation, which allows the bulk density to be
27 determined with a standard error of 0.136 and a 95% confidence interval ± 0.267. The
28 equation was developed from soils of S.E. Spain, as indicated above.
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34 SOC stocks according to soil type were obtained from the product of the SOCD of each
35 layer and the corresponding area covering each soil type. The area of each soil type was
36 taken from the Soil Map 1:100.000 of the LUCDEME Project (Faz Cano, 2003). The
37 total SOC stock in the first meter of the soil profile, for the study area, was obtained by
38 summing the stocks for each soil type.
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$$49 \quad \text{SOC stock} = \sum_i^n \text{SOCD}_i * \text{Area}_i \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

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54 Where n represent the numbers of soil types and i each soil type.
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1 SOC stocks according to land use were obtained by the product of the SOCD of each
2 layer and the total area covering each land use. In forestland and shrubland the stocks
3 for layers below 40 cm were corrected by the percentage of Leptosols (soils with
4 bedrock limitation to soil depth). The percentage of Leptosols, determined from the
5 LUCDEME Soil Map (Faz Cano, 2003), were 70% in forestland and 30% in shrubland.
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11 *2.5. Statistical analysis*

12 Prior to analysis, data were examined for normality by the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test
13 and homogeneity of variances by the Levené test. Data that were not distributed
14 normally were ln- transformed (precipitation, temperature and SOC concentration).
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16 The differences in SOC concentration between land uses, soil types and lithologies,
17 were examined by ANOVA using Tukey’s test for multiple pairwise comparisons. The
18 ANOVAs were conducted separately for different soil depths (0-20; 20-40, 40-60, 60-
19 100 cm). The relationships between SOC concentration and quantitative control factors
20 (precipitation, temperature, altitude, clay and clay plus fine silt) were examined through
21 correlation analysis. In addition, stepwise multiple regressions analysis with backward
22 and forward selection techniques was used to identify the main predictor variables
23 (Ramsey and Schafer, 1997). The entered variables were temperature, precipitation,
24 clay, fine silt and the categorical variable lithology as dummy variable, indicating for
25 each observation the presence (1) or absence (0) of a given parent material. We used
26 multiple linear regressions to test whether changes in the main predictor variables had a
27 positive, negative or neutral effect on SOC at each layer of the soil profile. All data
28 were analyzed using SPSS 13.0 software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois). Statistical
29 significance was set at $p < 0.05$.
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3.- Results

3.1.- Distribution of organic carbon concentration in the soil profiles

3.1.1. SOC concentration according to soil type and lithology

Significant differences in SOC concentration were found between the soil types of the uppermost layers (0-20 cm) (Table 1). Kastanozems (KS) and Leptosols (LP) showed the highest SOC concentrations followed by Cambisols (CM). Lower SOC concentrations occurred in Regosols (RG), Fluvisols (FL), Calcisols (CL), and Solonchaks (SC). Between 20 and 40 cm, KS, LP and CM were grouped together and below this depth less pronounced differences were obtained between soil types. FL showed the highest average SOC concentration in the deepest layer (60-100 cm), although, given the high value of the standard deviation, no significant differences with CL, SC and RG were observed. The coefficients of variation for SOC concentration, according to soil type, were very high (50-114%). Likewise, Batjes (1996) reported an average coefficient of variation of 79% for SOC in profiles grouped according to soil taxonomy orders. This high variability implies that other factors, in addition to soil type, are important for SOC concentration, and that the grouping of SOC data into large aggregated units may mask the influence of other control factors (Jobbagy and Jackson, 2000).

For all soil types, SOC concentration decreased significantly with depth. This vertical distribution of SOC concentration was fitted to a power function with R^2 values ranging between 0.19 and 0.46, depending on soil type, with $p < 0.001$ (Figure 1A). Different patterns in the vertical SOC distribution were observed among the soil types, the slope

1 of the curve being higher in KS and CM than in the rest of the soils. The specific soil
2 formation processes of each soil type were reflected in these SOC distributions through
3 the soil profiles, due to the genetic nature of soil classification system used. The most
4 contrasting behaviour was observed between FL and KS. FL displayed the lowest SOC
5 concentration at the surface and the highest in depth, while KS showed the highest SOC
6 concentration at surface and the lowest at 100 cm. This can be due to differences in the
7 soil formation processes. KS was developed from limestone under a dense vegetation
8 cover typical of Mediterranean forest. Due to the shallow root distribution of this
9 vegetation type the organic inputs into the soil occur mainly in the surface horizons
10 decreasing sharply with depth. However, FL was formed from alluvial stratified
11 sediments and is the result of different buried soils. The stratification in FL soils is
12 evident from the irregular decrease in the SOC content with depth (FAO, 2006). Similar
13 vertical distribution patterns of SOC to this study were found for CM, RG and FL in a
14 study of the major soil groups of Brazil (Batjes, 2005).

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34 The soils developed from quaternary sediments showed the highest SOC concentration
35 in the top 20 cm, although no significant differences were found with the metamorphic
36 sediments because of the high standard deviation of the former (Table 2). The soils from
37 marls and alluvial sediments displayed the lowest SOC concentration at this depth.
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44 However, in the 60-100 cm depth, the soils from alluvial sediments showed the highest
45 SOC concentration. The higher values in the subsoil (60-100 cm) for alluvial sediments
46 must be a consequence of the stratification, as indicated above for Fluvisols.
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53 *3.1.2. SOC concentration according to land use type*

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1 Significant differences in SOC concentration were found in the top 40 cm of the soil
2 according to land use (Table 3). Forest soils showed significantly higher values than
3 shrubland and cropland in the upper (0-20 and 20-40 cm) layers. SOC concentration in
4 forestland was more than three times higher in the top 20 cm and more the double in the
5 20-40 cm layer of the soil than in cropland. With regards to differences between
6 shrubland and cropland, the results indicated that the SOC concentration was
7 significantly higher in the top 40 cm of the shrubland soil. These results showed that the
8 conversion of forestland or shrubland to cultivation implies a reduction in SOC
9 concentration. This reduction was higher in the upper soil horizons and decreases in
10 intensity with soil depth. Below 40 cm depth no differences were found in SOC
11 concentration in relation to land use. The SOC concentration coefficient of variation
12 (CV) was always higher than 50% for all land use types and depths, ranging between
13 54% and 80% near surface and between 84% and 100% at 60-100cm depth, although, in
14 general, cropland showed lower CV than the other land uses at all depths (Table 3). As
15 indicated above, this high variability suggests that, being land use a very important
16 factor, there are other factors not tested in this study, (such as the percentage of vegetal
17 cover, microclimate conditions, or agricultural practices), which are also important for
18 the SOC concentration.

19 For all the land uses the SOC concentration decreased significantly with depth. The
20 vertical distribution of SOC concentration was fitted to a power function with R^2 values
21 between 0.28 and 0.52 depending on land use and $p < 0.001$ (Figure 1B). The relative
22 distribution of SOC concentration with depth was shallower in forestland than in the
23 other uses. This would reflect the different allocation of roots through the soil profile
24 according to vegetation types (Jobbagy and Jackson, 2000) or, in our case, land use.

3.2. Correlations between SOC concentration and environmental and textural variables

The ANOVA clearly showed that land use is a key factor in the SOC concentration of these semiarid soils. So, for a better understanding of the influence of the environmental and textural variables as control factors of SOC concentration, correlation analyses were performed separately for each land use (Table 4).

Different relationships were observed according to land use. In forestland, precipitation showed a strong correlation with SOC at all depths (r values between 0.51 and 0.62 at $p < 0.001$) and clay was positively correlated ($r=0.30$, $p < 0.10$) at 20-40 cm and ($r=0.62$, $p < 0.01$) at 40-60 cm depth. However, temperature and altitude were not correlated at any depth with SOC in this land use (Table 4). In shrubland, the environmental variables altitude and precipitation were correlated positively and temperature negatively with SOC between 0-60 cm, while below 60 cm depth only fine silt showed a significant correlation with SOC ($r=0.57$, $p < 0.01$). In cropland areas, the correlation coefficients between SOC concentration and control variables were, generally, lower than those in non-cultivated areas. Temperature was negatively correlated at all depths and altitude was positively correlated at nearly all depths. SOC was positively correlated with precipitation at 20-40 cm and 40-60 cm depths ($r=0.19$, $p < 0.05$) and with the clay content at 40-60 cm depth ($r=0.24$, $p < 0.05$). Overall, for all land uses, the textural factors only showed some correlation in the subsoil layers (below 20 cm).

3.3. Regression models of SOC concentration

With the stepwise multiple regression analysis, we examined the relationships between SOC concentration and the following predictor variables: lithology, precipitation, temperature, clay, and fine silt. This analysis was accomplished for forestland, shrubland and cropland separately at four different depth layers. Significant differences

1 were found in the relative importance of the predictor variables according to soil use
2 and depth (Table 5).
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4 In forestland, precipitation and texture (clay) were the main predictor variables
5 explaining the SOC variability at the different depths. Precipitation explained 15% and
6 12% of the SOC variability at 0-20 and 20-40 cm depth, respectively. Clay explained
7 40% of SOC variability between 40 and 60 cm depth and precipitation plus clay
8 explained 45% of the SOC variability below 60 cm. In this use the model does not
9 selected the temperature and lithology.
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19 In shrubland, 36% of SOC variability was explained by temperature and lithology in the
20 0-20 cm layer and 39% in the 20-40 cm interval. Temperature was the main predictor
21 variable at 40-60 cm and lithology plus fine silt explained 33% of the variability.
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26 In cropland soils the R^2 values were, in general, lower than in the other land uses and
27 decreased with depth. The most significant factors controlling SOC concentration in
28 cropland were lithology (marls), texture (fine silt or clay) and temperature at 0-40 cm
29 depth, marls plus clay at 40-60 cm depth and quaternary sediments below 60 cm depth.
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39 *3.4. Distribution of organic carbon stocks in the soil profiles*

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41 The total SOC stored in the top 1 m of the soil in the Murcia Province was about 79 Tg
42 (Teragram), with a mean density of about 7 kg C m⁻³ (Tables 6 and 7). The vertical
43 distribution was shallow, with more than 70% stored in the top 40 cm of the soil.
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48 The soils types with highest SOCD in the top 1 m were CM and KS, followed by FL
49 and CL (Table 6). In the case of LP it must be taken into account that soil depth is
50 limited by taxonomic characteristics (FAO, 2006). The vertical distribution of SOCD
51 was deepest in FL and shallowest in KS, which is consistent with their vegetal cover
52 and soil formation processes as discussed above. Considering the area covered by every
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1 soil type in the Murcia Province, only the Calcisols stored half of the total SOC (Figure
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4 According to land use, although the highest SOCD was found in forestland (Table 7),
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6 considering the total area covered by each use, the greater amount of SOC was stored in
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8 cropland (48.9%), followed by forestland (31.5%) and shrubland (19.6%) (Figure 2B).
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10 The vertical distribution showed marked differences among the uses, being shallowest
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12 in forestland and deepest in cropland, which is in agreement with the results reported by
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14 other researchers (Yang et al. 2007). The top 40 cm contained 87% of the SOC stored in
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16 forestland, while in cropland the SOC in this layer accounted for the 63.5% (Table 7).
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18 Of the total SOC stored in the study area below 40 cm depth, 63% occurred in cropland
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20 and only 15% was found in forestland. Subsoil forestland SOC (below 40 cm depth)
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22 contributed only 4% to the total SOC stored in the region, while this contribution from
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24 cropland was 18%. This was due to the bedrock limitation to soil depth and the greater
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26 stoniness of forestland.
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36 **4. Discussion**

37 38 39 40 41 *4.1. SOC concentration*

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45 The results of this study suggest that land use type will be of great importance in the
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47 impact of global change on SOC concentration in semiarid areas. Although several
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49 studies have proved that changes in land uses involve changes in SOC content (Post and
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51 Kwon, 2000), considerable uncertainties remain as to the magnitude of these changes in
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53 different regions (Schimel et al. 2002). In our study area, the average SOC
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55 concentration (Table 3) near the surface (0- 20 cm) was more than three times higher in
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1 forestland (30.4 g.kg⁻¹) than in cropland (9.1 g.kg⁻¹), so a very important reduction of
2 SOC concentration, in the top 20 cm of the soil may be expected following a change
3 from forestland to cropland, if actions are not taken to protect the SOC accumulated
4 under forestland. This SOC reduction implies an average emission to the atmosphere of
5 1ton of carbon (3.66 tons of CO₂) per 47 tons of surface forestland soil converted to
6 cropland. Other authors found land cover to be a key predictor variable of SOC
7 concentration and stock in arid and semiarid areas (Lo Seen et al. 2010, Wiesmeier et al.
8 2011; Hoffmann et. al. 2012). Boix Fayos et al. (2009) found similar losses of SOC in
9 the first 20 cm of soil when forest was converted to cropland in an area located at the
10 north of the Murcia Province. The conversion from forest to cultivated areas reduce the
11 surface SOC concentration mainly through reducing biomass inputs into the soil,
12 increasing soil erosion rates and accelerating the decomposition of soil organic matter.
13 Some examples of these effects in Murcia Province have been quantified in others
14 studies (Martínez-Mena et al. 2002; Almagro et al. 2010). In addition, there are
15 evidences that the magnitude of this loss of SOC through cultivation in semiarid areas
16 could be greater than in more humid areas (Celik, 2005; Martinez Mena et al. 2008).
17 This impact decreased with depth. So, in the 20-40 cm interval the loss in SOC
18 concentration was 53% and no differences in SOC concentration were observed
19 between land uses below 60 cm depth (Table 3). Therefore, little changes may be
20 expected in deeper SOC concentration following the conversion of forestland into
21 cropland.

22 The SOC according to parent material showed lower average concentration in soils
23 developed from marls than in the rest of the soils, although no significant differences
24 could be established, in all cases, due to the high standard deviation (Table 2). The
25 chemical, physical and mineralogical properties of the parent material play an important

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role in the composition and amount of organic matter stored in the soil. In environmental conditions similar to those of this study, Turrion et al. (2009) reported that bedrock type was the principal factor affecting soil development and the fertility of forest soil in central western Spain. Also, Aranda et al (2011), found that the evolution of soil organic matter to more stable and evolved forms of humus was less pronounced in soils from marls than in soils derived from colluvial limestones, which might lead to a faster turnover rate and lower SOC content in marly soils. On the other hand, the high susceptibility to soil erosion could reduce SOC accumulation through the removal of surface litter particles attached to SOC (Lal, 2004), a fact corroborated by Liu et al. (2011), in semiarid areas of the Loess Plateau, China. In arid and semiarid Mediterranean areas, since soils derived from marls are very susceptible to erosion (Imeson et al. 1998), we suggest that the lowest content of SOC in marly soils is mainly attributable to the removal of surface particles by water erosion, which is accelerated by the very poor vegetal cover due to the low soil fertility.

4.2. *Factors controlling SOC concentration variability*

The results of the stepwise multivariate regression between SOC concentration and environmental and textural control factors (Table 5), for the different depth intervals, showed that the relative importance of each factor changed with depth and with land use type. Similar results were reported by Jobbagy and Jackson (2000). This suggests that the control factors or their relative importance and the mechanisms involved in the stabilization and dynamics of SOC may be different at the surface and in subsurface soil

1 (Salome et al. 2010; Rumpel and Kögel-Knabner, 2011), and also may change
2 depending on land use.
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4 Better relationships between the control factors and SOC concentration were obtained in
5 the deeper layers than in the surface layers in forestland. In this use, the main factor
6 controlling SOC was precipitation to 40 cm depth, clay content at 40-60 cm, and
7 precipitation plus clay below 60 cm depth. In shrubland and cropland, temperature and
8 lithology were the main control factors explaining the variability of SOC concentration
9 through the soil profile. In general, in all the soil uses the relative importance of climatic
10 factors (precipitation and temperature) decreased with depth, while the importance of
11 textural factors (clay and fine silt) and lithology increased.
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24 As regards predictions of the impact of climatic change according to land use, our
25 results point to decreasing SOC concentrations as precipitation becomes less, which was
26 evident at all depths in forestland. This can be attributed to the key role of precipitation
27 in biomass productivity, which is the determinant of litter input (Chaplot et al. 2010).
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29 However, the relative importance of precipitation decreases with depth and the relative
30 weight of texture increases. This may be due to the higher stabilization of organic
31 matter through organo-mineral associations (Torn et al. 1997, Six et al. 2002) in deeper
32 layers than at the surface. In shrublands and croplands a reduction of SOC with
33 increasing temperature was evident at all depths. In shrubland, precipitation showed a
34 positive correlation with SOC concentration in the Pearson correlation coefficient
35 (Table 4) but no in the stepwise regression (Table 5), while no impact of precipitation
36 was observed in cropland. This result might be due, in the case of cultivated areas, to
37 the irrigation carried out in most of the areas considered in this study.
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1 In cropland, a very low percentage of variation of SOC can be explained by the
2 variables considered. The weak relationships obtained might be due to the wide range of
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5 crops and management techniques covered by this land use.
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7 In relation with the predictions of the impact of global warming on SOC concentration,
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10 our results also suggest differences according to land use and depth. In cropland and
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13 shrubland, losses of SOC concentration can be predicted to occur with increases in
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16 temperature (Table 4 and 5). Similar results were reported by other authors (Leifeld et
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19 al. 2005, Garten and Hanson, 2006, Yang et al. 2007). These results might be
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22 attributable to the greater increase in decomposition rate compared with the increase in
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25 photosynthesis due to temperature increase, which is particularly favoured when soils
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28 are intensively managed (Balkovic et al. 2011), as occur in cropland. This effect of
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31 temperature on the mechanisms controlling the C dynamic was different with depth,
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34 being more evident at the upper soil layers (Table 5). Likewise, Jobbagy and Jackson
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37 (2000) found a decreasing correlation between SOC and temperature as depth increased
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40 and suggested that temperature may have a proportionally higher effect on the
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43 decomposition of shallow SOC than on deep SOC. The different temperature
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46 sensitivities between surface and deep SOC found in this study may be attributable to
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49 changes in the kinetic properties of soil organic compounds due to the greater physical
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52 and chemical protection in depth (Davidson and Janssen, 2006). The higher correlation
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55 between SOC and the clay content found in deep layers support this affirmation.
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59 The feedbacks between SOC and climate are not fully understood (Schmidt et al. 2011).

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62 In contrast with croplands and shrublands, the lack of correlation between T and SOC,
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65 at any depth, in forestland suggests that no effect on SOC in forestland is to be expected
in short-term, with the current trend in global warming. This may be due to the increase
in net ecosystem productivity (NEP) with increased atmospheric CO₂ and global

1 warming (Cao et al. 1998; Melillo et al. 2011), which could compensate the warming-
2 induced SOC losses through the gain of vegetal input in the soil. In any case, these
3 results should be considered with care because: a) the increase in NEP will decline as
4 the CO₂ fertilization effect becomes saturated (Cao et al. 1998), so, the long-term
5 prediction could be different; and b) the sensitivity of SOC to changes in T is less in
6 non-perturbed soils (soils at their native temperature) than in perturbed soils (Agren and
7 Bosata, 2002). This could mean that the effect of temperature in forestland could be
8 masked by other factors.
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24 *4.3. SOC stocks*

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29 Considering the entire soil profile (1 m) the average SOCD was 8.4, 8.1 and 6.3 kg m⁻³
30 in forestland, shrubland and cropland, respectively (Table 7). From these results,
31 estimated losses of SOC from the conversion of forestland into cropland were about
32 25%, and from shrubland into cropland about 21%. Our results agree with those
33 reported by Davidson and Ackerman, (1993), who estimated losses of between 20% and
34 40% of SOC stocks following the conversion of areas with perennial vegetation
35 (grassland and forest) into cultivated areas.
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46 Given that our results, in agreement with the other studies mentioned above, predict that
47 the impact of climate change on SOC will be larger in surface soils than in depth, we
48 suggest that the strategies for C sequestration in semiarid areas should be focused on
49 subsoil C sequestration. Both, the reforestation of degraded forestland and the adoption
50 of recommended management practices (RMPs) in cropland and grazing land, have
51 been advocated as effective options for C sequestration in soils (Smith, 2004), and both
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1 lead to additional environmental and socio-economic benefits (UNEP, 2012). The
2 choice between different options to achieve the best win-win outcomes in environment-
3 development programs is frequently difficult to make (Simon et al. 2012). Taking into
4 account the number of factors and complexity involved in this issue, it seems reasonable
5 to think that the best options may change according to the specific conditions of each
6 area. The vertical distribution of SOC stocks showed that subsoil forestland (below 40
7 cm depth) contributed only 4.4% to the total SOC stored in the study area, while
8 cropland contributed 17.8% and shrubland 6.6% of total SOC. This was due to the fact
9 that forestlands in arid and semiarid areas are usually confined to mountainous areas, in
10 which the soil capacity for C sequestration is restricted to shallow soil profiles due to
11 bedrock limitation to soil depth. In these situations, the option of C sequestration and
12 improvement in soil productivity through implementation of RMPs in cropland and
13 shrubland soils might be economically and environmentally more profitable than
14 reforestation, unless reforestation is carried out in deep soils of marginal areas. As
15 reported Alvaro-Fuentes and Paustian (2012), under climate change conditions, Spanish
16 agricultural soils could act as potential atmospheric C sinks. Note that, although SOCD
17 was higher in forestland than in cropland and shrubland, the potential capacity for
18 additional C sequestration is higher in cropland and shrubland soils due to their deeper
19 soil profiles and lower C saturation.

20 This suggestion could be extrapolable to large areas in arid and semiarid conditions
21 since Leptosols, the most extensive reference soil group on Earth, are particularly
22 abundant in mountains in the extensive desert regions of North Africa and Southwest
23 Asia (Spaargaren, 2008). An increase of 1 ton of soil carbon pool of degraded cropland
24 soils may increase crop yield by 20 to 40 kg ha⁻¹ for wheat (Lal, 2004). Restoration of
25 degraded cropland soils is, therefore, a key aspect for a sustainable development and to

1 meet basic needs of the present and future population (Lal, 2010). More research, at
2 regional scale, seems to be necessary to implement appropriate public policies able to
3 manage the synergies between climate change, soil degradation and sustainable
4 development in different environmental and socio-economic conditions.
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10 11 **5. Conclusion**

12 The average density of SOC in these semiarid areas was low ($\approx 7 \text{ kg C m}^{-3}$) in the 0-100
13 cm layer, and more than 70% was located in the top 40 cm. Land use was the main
14 factor controlling SOC concentration in these semiarid areas. The conversion of
15 forestland to cropland involves a substantial decrease in SOC concentration and it
16 should be strictly restricted in these areas. The analysis of environmental control factors
17 suggested a negative effect on the SOC concentration in a climatic change scenario with
18 increased temperature and a decrease in rainfall, as expected in semiarid areas. The
19 results showed that this impact would be much greater in surface than in the subsurface
20 SOC. Therefore, the strategies for soil C sequestration should be focused on subsoil
21 sequestration. In this way, the potential capacity of large areas of forestlands will be
22 limited due to bedrock impediments to soil depth. Appropriate management practices in
23 croplands and shrublands, which have deep soil profiles with low organic C saturation,
24 seem to be a win-win option for sequestering atmospheric CO_2 and improve soil
25 productivity.
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Table 1. Mean, standard deviation (SD) and coefficient of variation (CV) of SOC grouped by soil type at different depths.

Soil type	SOC (g kg ⁻¹)							
	0-20 cm		20-40 cm		40-60 cm		60-100 cm	
	Mean±SD	CV	Mean±SD	CV	Mean±SD	CV	Mean±SD	CV
Calcisols	12.2±7.4 ^{a,b}	60	7.0±4.4 ^{ab}	63	3.6±2.2 ^{ab}	61	2.2±1.6 ^a	72
Regosols	10.8±9.1 ^a	84	5.3±4.4 ^a	83	2.9±2.0 ^a	69	2.6±1.7 ^{ab}	65
Cambisols	23.5±20.3 ^{bc}	86	14.9±10.3 ^b	70	6.8±4.4 ^b	65	4.1±3.7 ^{ab}	90
Fluvisols	10.1±6.6 ^{a,b}	66	7.1±4.5 ^{ab}	63	4.6±3.2 ^{ab}	69	4.6±3.8 ^b	83
Kastanozems	31.5±18.6 ^c	58	18.3±14.7 ^b	80	3.7±2.6 ^{ab}	70	2.1±2.4 ^a	114
Leptosols	29.2± 18.0 ^c	62	10.5±6.3 ^b	60	-	-	-	-
Solonchaks	11.3±5.7 ^{a,b}	50	8.5±7.8 ^{ab}	92	3.8±2.2 ^{ab}	58	4.3±3.4 ^{ab}	79

Different low cases within columns means significant differences between soil types at each depth at $p < 0.05$ according to Tukey test.

Table 2. Mean, standard deviation (SD) and coefficient of variation (CV) of SOC grouped by lithology at different depths.

Lithology	SOC (g kg ⁻¹)							
	0-20 cm		20-40 cm		40-60 cm		60-100 cm	
	Mean±SD	CV	Mean±SD	CV	Mean±SD	CV	Mean±SD	CV
Quaternary sediments	19.1±16.5 ^b	86	10.6±9.5 ^b	89	4.2±4.2 ^b	100	2.9±2.7 ^a	93
Alluvial sediments	9.8±6.0 ^a	61	6.7±4.8 ^{a,b}	72	4.5±3.3 ^b	73	4.6±3.9 ^b	85
Marls	9.3±7.3 ^a	78	6.1±5.2 ^a	85	3.0±2.2 ^a	73	2.3±1.6 ^a	69
Metamorphic sediments	12.3±5.9 ^{a,b}	50	6.6±5.4 ^{a,b}	81	4.3±1.8 ^{a,b}	41	3.3±1.8 ^{a,b}	54

Different low cases within columns means significant differences between different lithologies at each depth at $p < 0.05$ according to Tukey test.

Table 3. Mean, standard deviation (SD) and coefficient of variation (CV) of SOC grouped by land use at different depths.

Land use	0-20 cm			20-40 cm			40-60 cm			60-100 cm		
	Mean±SD	CV		Mean±SD	CV		Mean±SD	CV		Mean±SD	CV	
Forestland	30.4±19.5 ^c	64		13.4±11.2 ^c	83		5.8±4.6 ^a	79		4.4±3.7 ^a	84	
Shrubland	17.4±13.9 ^b	80		9.9±9.1 ^b	92		4.6±4.4 ^a	96		3.2±3.2 ^a	100	
Cropland	9.1±4.9 ^a	54		6.2±4.0 ^a	64		3.4±2.3 ^a	68		3.1±2.8 ^a	90	

Different low cases means significant differences in depth between land uses at each depth at $p < 0.05$ according to Tukey test.

Table 4. Pearson correlations coefficients between SOC and environmental variables at different depths in each land use.

SOC content by depth (cm)	Environmental variables				
	Clay	Fine silt	Altitude	Temperature	Precipitation
Forestland					
0-20	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.53**
20-40	0.30	ns	ns	ns	0.51**
40-60	0.62**	ns	ns	ns	0.54**
60-100	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.62**
Shrubland					
0-20	ns	ns	0.53**	-0.54**	0.53*
20-40	ns	ns	0.55**	-0.58**	0.51*
40-60	ns	ns	0.43**	-0.45**	0.27**
60-100	ns	0.57**	ns	ns	ns
Cropland					
0-20	ns	ns	0.22**	-0.20*	ns
20-40	ns	ns	0.21**	-0.27**	0.19*
40-60	0.24*	ns	ns	-0.18	0.19
60-100	ns	ns	0.26*	-0.29**	ns

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.001$; in bold $p < 0.1$; ns: not significant correlation.

Table 5. Stepwise multivariate regression model of SOC against predictor variables at different depths and land uses.

Land use	Depth increments (cm)	Term	Unstandard coefficient	Standard coefficient	R ² adj.	P-value
Forestland	0-20	Intercept	-3.96		0.15	0.008
		lnP	0.85	0.37		
	20-40	Intercept	-5.76		0.12	0.027
		lnP	0.99	0.38		
	40-60	Intercept	-2.48		0.40	0.000
		Clay	0.06	0.53		
	60-100	Intercept	-16.10		0.45	0.003
		lnP	2.67	0.63		
		Clay	0.06	0.54		
Shrubland	0-20	Intercept	10.26		0.36	0.000
		lnT	-2.94	-0.46		
		L ₁	0.75	0.44		
		L ₂	0.51	0.18		
	20-40	Intercept	11.77		0.39	0.000
		lnT	-3.48	-0.41		
		L ₂	-0.58	-0.24		
		L ₃	-0.89	-0.35		
	40-60	Intercept	9.18		0.10	0.008
		lnT	-2.80	-0.34		
		L ₄	-0.74	-0.30		
	60-100	Intercept	-0.54		0.33	0.000
		L ₁	-0.64	-0.35		
		Fine silt	0.02	0.41		
	Cropland	0-20	Intercept	6.33		0.21
L ₃			-0.61	-0.41		
Fine silt			0.012	0.21		
lnT			-1.59	-0.23		
20-40		Intercept	7.04		0.16	0.000
		L ₃	-0.76	-0.34		
		Cl	0.016	0.21		
		lnT	-2.05	-0.19		
40-60		Intercept	0.44		0.18	0.000
		L ₃	-0.91	-0.39		
		Clay	0.025	0.34		
60-100		Intercept	1.24		0.11	0.002
		L ₁	-0.66	-0.35		

T^a: mean annual temperature; P: mean annual precipitation; L: lithology type: L₁: Quaternary sediments; L₂: Alluvial sediments; L₃: Marls; L₄: Metamorphic sediments.

Table 6. Mean and standard deviation of SOC density (SOCD) and total SOC stock in each soil type.

Soil type	Land area (10 ⁶ m ²)	SOCD (kg m ⁻²)										Total SOC storage (10 ¹² g)				
		Depth (cm)										Depth (cm)				
		0-20	20-40	40-60	60-100	0-100	0-20	20-40	40-60	60-100	0-100	20-40	40-60	60-100	0-100	
Calcisols	5521	3.0 ± 1.2 ^{ab}	1.8 ± 0.9 ^{ab}	0.9 ± 0.6 ^a	1.3 ± 0.4 ^{ab}	7.0	17.0	5.0	7.2	39.2	10.0	5.0	7.2	39.2		
Regosols	2100	2.6 ± 1.5 ^a	1.5 ± 1.0 ^a	0.8 ± 0.5 ^a	1.4 ± 0.3 ^{ab}	6.3	5.4	1.7	3.0	13.3	3.2	1.7	3.0	13.3		
Leptosols	1986	4.1 ± 1.2 ^c	2.6 ± 1.1 ^{ab,c}	-	-	6.7	8.1	-	-	13.3	5.2	-	-	13.3		
Fluvisols	1144	2.7 ± 1.4 ^a	1.9 ± 1.1 ^{ab}	1.5 ± 0.8 ^{ab}	2.7 ± 0.8 ^b	8.8	3.1	1.7	3.1	10.1	2.2	1.7	3.1	10.1		
Cambisols	214	3.9 ± 1.7 ^{b,c}	3.1 ± 1.6 ^{b,c}	1.9 ± 1.1 ^b	2.3 ± 0.8 ^{ab}	11.2	0.9	0.4	0.5	2.5	0.7	0.4	0.5	2.5		
Solonchaks	29	2.7 ± 1.2 ^a	1.9 ± 0.8 ^{ab}	0.9 ± 0.4 ^a	1.4 ± 0.6 ^{ab}	6.9	0.08	0.03	0.04	0.2	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.2		
Kastanozems	10	4.8 ± 1.5 ^c	3.3 ± 1.7 ^c	1.2 ± 0.7 ^{ab}	1.1 ± 0.6 ^{ab}	10.4	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.1	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.1		
Total	11004						34.63	8.84	13.85	78.7	21.39	8.84	13.85	78.7		

Different low cases within columns means significant differences between soil types at each depth at p<0.05 according to Tukey test.

Table 7. Mean and standard deviation of SOC density (SOC_D) and total SOC storage in each land use and depth.

Land use	Land area (10 ⁶ m ²)	SOC _D (kg m ⁻²)						Total SOC storage (10 ¹² g)				
		Depth (cm)						Depth (cm)				
		0-20	20-40	40-60	60-100	0-100	0-20	20-40	40-60	60-100	0-100	
Forestland	2963	4.6±1.5 ^c	2.7±1.6 ^b	0.5±0.1 ^b	0.6±0.1 ^a	8,4	13.6	8.0	1.5	1.8	24.9	
Shrubland	1898	3.3±1.6 ^b	2.1±1.6 ^a	1.2±1.0 ^{a,b}	1.5±1.4 ^a	8,2	6.3	4.0	2.3	2.9	15.5	
Cropland	6143	2.3 ±1.1 ^a	1.7±0.9 ^a	0.9±0.6 ^a	1.4±1.1 ^a	6,3	14.1	10.4	5.5	8.6	38.6	
Total	11004						34.0	22.4	9.3	13.3	79.0	

Different low cases within columns means significant differences between land uses at each depth at p<0.05 according to Tukey test.

Figure 1: Vertical distribution of SOC concentration (g kg^{-1}) in the soil profile of different soil types (A) and land uses (B). Note that the lines represent the connection between plots of the data, not the regression lines.

Figure 2: Percentage of SOC stored at 0-100 cm soil layer under different soil types (A) and land uses (B).

Figure 1

Figure 2

